

Development of a Laboratory Testbed for Cybersecurity Evaluation of Distribution Substations Using Open Source Tools

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel approach to developing a laboratory testbed for cybersecurity testing distribution substations, focusing on the GOOSE communication protocol specified by IEC 61850. The testbed uniquely employs open-source tools to accurately replicate the operational conditions of a real substation, utilizing Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs) with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 7. This combination ensures high fidelity to real-world applications while maintaining a safe and isolated environment. A significant novelty of this research lies in its ability to use TRL 7-level equipment and integrate diverse open-source tools, which enhances the realism and applicability of cybersecurity tests. Substations' increasing digitization and automation introduces new cybersecurity vulnerabilities that could disrupt power distribution, underscoring the necessity for robust security measures. The developed testbed offers a vital platform for rigorously testing and improving cybersecurity defences, safeguarding critical infrastructure against evolving threats. This comprehensive approach addresses existing challenges and sets a new standard for future research and development in substation cybersecurity.

Index Terms—GOOSE, IED, open source tools, cybersecurity

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological evolution of power systems has significantly integrated advanced communication protocols and digital devices within substation automation systems. The IEC 61850 standard is crucial in this field, defining communication protocols for IEDs in substations. These protocols, including GOOSE, Sampled Value (SV), and Manufacturing Message Specification (MMS), facilitate efficient and reliable communication for protection, control, and monitoring within substation environments.

The transition from traditional electromechanical relays to multifunctional IEDs has brought numerous benefits, such as improved flexibility, interoperability, and enhanced protection schemes. However, this digitisation also introduces new cybersecurity challenges. The GOOSE protocol is critical for substation automation, enabling fast, reliable horizontal com-

munication between IEDs at the bay level [1]. Given the strict time requirements for GOOSE message delivery, ensuring the protocol's security and resilience against cyberattacks is crucial.

Cybersecurity testing of substation communication protocols is essential to identify vulnerabilities that could be exploited by malicious actors, potentially leading to significant disruptions in power delivery and grid stability [2]. Traditional testing methods often rely on live substation environments, which pose risks of unintended interference with operational systems [3]. While many existing testing approaches employ simulated or virtual IEDs to assess the cybersecurity of substation communication protocols [1], [4], these methods have limitations. Simulated IEDs often lack the full complexity and nuance of their real-world counterparts, leading to results that may not fully capture the operational challenges and vulnerabilities in actual substation environments. Consequently, findings derived from these simulations may not be entirely usable for practical applications or for developing robust cybersecurity measures [5]. This underscores the importance of using physical IEDs in laboratory testbeds to ensure that testing scenarios and outcomes are as realistic and applicable as possible.

This paper presents the development of a laboratory testbed designed for comprehensive cybersecurity testing of distribution substations, focusing on the GOOSE protocol as specified by the IEC 61850 standard. By utilising open-source tools, this testbed aims to provide a cost-effective, flexible, and safe environment for evaluating the cybersecurity resilience of substation communication protocols. The testbed employs IEDs TRL 7 to ensure high fidelity to real-world applications, facilitating rigorous and realistic testing scenarios. The main contributions of this paper are:

- Reviewing and summarizing the main characteristics of the GOOSE protocol (Section 2).
- Conducting a comparative study of the available open

source tools used for substation IED communication and GOOSE packet operations (Section 3).

- Simulating a substation environment and communication using open source tools (Section 4).
- Testing the online GOOSE communication and cybersecurity threats using the previously developed environment (Section 5).
- Developing a laboratory testbed for cybersecurity evaluation of distribution substations using TRL 7 level equipment (Section 6).

This research highlights the importance of such testbeds in addressing the evolving cyber threats faced by the power sector and underscores the need for continuous advancements in cybersecurity practices to protect critical infrastructure. By providing a dedicated platform for testing and enhancing cybersecurity measures, this work contributes to the overall robustness and security of modern power networks.

II. GOOSE PROTOCOL OVERVIEW

The GOOSE protocol, defined by the IEC 61850 standard, plays a critical role in the automation and protection of electrical substations. This section explores the essential characteristics of GOOSE, its message structure, and the timing mechanism crucial for its operation in substation environments.

GOOSE messages enable high-speed, reliable, and event-driven communication between IEDs in substations. These messages are broadcasted over the network to multiple IEDs using a multicast MAC address, ensuring that critical status updates and commands are promptly shared among all relevant devices.

A. Message Architecture

A GOOSE message follows a structured format that ensures efficient data transmission. The architecture of a GOOSE message is presented by IEC 61850-8-1 standard, and includes [6]:

- Destination MAC Address: A multicast address reserved for IEC 61850 applications.
- Source MAC Address: The MAC address of the publishing IED.
- Priority Tagging/VLAN ID: Ensures priority handling within network traffic.
- Ethertype: Indicates the type of protocol, set to 88-B8 for GOOSE.
- Application ID (APPID): Identifies the specific application generating the message.
- GOOSE Protocol Data Unit (goosePDU): Contains various subfields, including:
 - gocbRef: GOOSE control block reference.
 - timeAllowedtoLive: Maximum time a receiver waits before declaring communication failure.
 - dataSet: Data set name.
 - goID: GOOSE ID for the message.
 - stNum: State number, incrementing with each new event.
 - sqNum: Sequence number, incrementing with each retransmission.
 - confRev: Configuration revision number.
 - ndsCom: Needs commissioning indicator.

- numDatSetEntries: Number of data entries.
- allData: Actual data being transmitted, such as status values and measurements.

B. Timing Scheme

The GOOSE protocol employs a specific timing scheme to manage the transmission of messages. This scheme is crucial for maintaining the reliability and promptness required for substation protection and control. The timing behavior of GOOSE messages is illustrated in Fig. 1. This figure depicts

Fig. 1: GOOSE timing mechanism [7].

the timing behavior of GOOSE messages, showing the initial transmission interval T_0 and the progressive increase in intervals following an event (e.g. T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , ...) until it stabilizes back to T_0 .

The timing mechanism is vital for GOOSE messages to handle the burst of communication effectively, particularly during faults or other significant events in the substation [8]. The retransmission intervals are configured based on the criticality of the information and the network's operational parameters.

C. Configuring IEDs for GOOSE Communication

The first step in configuring an IED for GOOSE communication involves setting up the GOOSE data set. This data set comprises a list of data attributes, such as status indications, measurements, and control commands, which the IED will publish. The data attributes are defined according to the IEC 61850 data model, ensuring compatibility and interoperability across different devices and systems. The Substation Configuration Language (SCL) files play a crucial role here, providing a structured format for defining these attributes and their relationships within the IED.

Once the data set is established, the next step is configuring the GOOSE Control Block (GCB). The GCB defines how the data set will be transmitted over the network. Key parameters include the destination MAC address, which determines the multicast address used for broadcasting the GOOSE messages, and the Application Identifier (APPID), which uniquely identifies the GOOSE messages generated by the IED. The GCB also includes settings for the retransmission intervals, specifying how frequently the messages are resent to ensure reliability and timely updates during critical events.

The IEDs must be programmed to handle the specific timing requirements of GOOSE communication. This involves setting the initial transmission interval T_0 and configuring the sequence of retransmission intervals that follow an event. These intervals ensure that messages are promptly retransmitted in burst mode during an event and gradually return to the periodic transmission rate T_0 once stability is restored. This

intervals should fall in the range of 3 ms to 20 ms and should be carefully chosen to avoid GOOSE storm (an excessive number of GOOSE messages are generated and transmitted in a short period overwhelming the network infrastructure).

To enable seamless communication, the IEDs must also be configured to subscribe to GOOSE messages from other devices. This involves specifying which GOOSE messages the IED should listen for and process, based on their MAC addresses and APPIDs. The IED uses this information to filter incoming messages, ensuring that only relevant data is processed and acted upon.

III. OPEN SOURCE TOOLS FOR SUBSTATION SIMULATION AND COMMUNICATION

Open source tools play a crucial role in the development, testing, and analysis of GOOSE communication within substation automation systems. These tools provide functionalities that support the configuration, simulation, monitoring, and security testing of GOOSE messages and the overall network infrastructure. The primary functions of these open source tools include:

- **Configuration:** tools that enable the configuration of IEDs, including the setup of GOOSE control blocks and data sets: IEDExplorer [9], OpenPLC61850 [10], SCL Manipulator and Configuration [11]
- **Simulation:** tools that allow for the creation of virtual environments that mimic real-world substation conditions, providing a safe space to test configurations and scenarios without impacting live systems: OpenSCD [12], IEC61850-open-server [13], OpenMUC [14], rapid61850 [15]
- **Protocol Testing and Validation:** tools that are used to validate the implementation of the IEC 61850 standard and ensure that GOOSE messages conform to the protocol specifications: IEDExplorer, OpenSCD.
- **Network Traffic Analysis:** Monitoring and analyzing network traffic is essential for understanding the behavior of GOOSE messages and identifying potential issues: Wireshark [16], Snort [17]

A. IEDScout

IEDScout is a versatile tool for analyzing, testing, and configuring IEC 61850-enabled IEDs in substation automation systems. It supports the simulation of IEDs, detailed protocol analysis for GOOSE, MMS, and SV, and real-time communication monitoring. IEDScout's user-friendly interface simplifies complex tasks, while its visualization features aid in troubleshooting and diagnosing network issues. It ensures interoperability, supports configuration management, and provides detailed reporting. Security features help monitor and maintain communication integrity. All its features can be accessed on a Windows workstation. Although support for Linux and other operating systems has been discontinued, IEDScout can still be installed and used on these platforms using the Wine emulation layer and Bottles, but without the network specific functions.

B. OpenPLC61850

OpenPLC61850 is an extension to the OpenPLC software designed to facilitate the simulation and analysis of IEC

61850 communication protocols, which are critical for smart grid research. This tool is particularly useful for modeling substation communication networks, supporting the testing and validation of protocols like GOOSE, MMS, and Sampled Values. OpenPLC61850 enables real-time data exchange and provides detailed protocol analysis, making it an essential resource for understanding network performance and reliability.

C. SCL Manipulator and Configuration

SCL Manipulation and Configuration Tools is a comprehensive set of libraries and applications designed for creating and modifying XML files using Substation Configuration Language based on the IEC 61850-6 standard. These tools support the editing, validation, and visualization of SCL files, including Substation Configuration Descriptions (SCD), Configured IED Descriptions (CID), and Instantiated IED Descriptions (ICD). The user-friendly interface allows for efficient configuration and debugging of substation automation systems. The tools facilitate the management of logical nodes, data objects, and communication configurations, enhancing the interoperability and functionality of IEC 61850-compliant systems.

D. OpenSCD

OpenSCD is an open-source substation configuration description editor designed for projects utilizing the IEC 61850-6 Edition 2 standard or later. It provides a browser-based platform for editing SCL files, facilitating the creation, modification, and validation of substation automation system configurations. OpenSCD supports the configuration of logical nodes, data sets, and communication parameters, ensuring interoperability and compliance with IEC 61850 standards. Its user-friendly interface and extensive feature set allow for efficient substation configuration and debugging. The tool is easily accessible online and can be installed locally or on private web servers for broader deployment flexibility.

E. OpenServer

OpenServer is an open-source implementation of an IEC 61850 server, utilizing the libiec61850 library [18]. It simulates various IEDs, allowing for comprehensive testing and validation of substation automation systems. The server supports functionalities like GOOSE messaging, SV, and MMS, facilitating real-time data exchange and protection schemes. OpenServer uses Docker for containerized deployment, enhancing flexibility and scalability. It includes features for simulating process values using pySpice, creating a closed-loop system between simulation models and IED functions. Notably, it operates exclusively offline, ensuring a secure and controlled testing environment.

F. OpenMUC

OpenMUC is a software framework based on Java and OSGi, designed to simplify the development of customized monitoring, logging, and controlling systems. It supports a wide range of communication protocols including Modbus, IEC 61850, IEC 60870-5-104, and more. OpenMUC enables easy application development by providing an abstract service for data access, allowing developers to focus on application

logic rather than communication details. It features dynamic configuration through a central file, a configuration service, or a web interface. Additionally, OpenMUC supports data logging in various formats, making it suitable for both simple data loggers and complex SCADA systems.

G. Rapid61850

Rapid61850 is an open-source project designed for the rapid prototyping of protection and control schemes using the IEC 61850 standard. It converts SCL files into C code, facilitating the implementation and communication of various IEDs, even on platforms like Raspberry Pi. The project includes comprehensive configuration steps using Eclipse IDE to set up and generate code. However, significant time and effort were required to adapt the provided instructions to the latest versions of Ubuntu 24.04 and Eclipse 2024-03 on a Raspberry Pi 4 with 8GB of RAM. Despite following all steps, the build process ultimately failed due to missing file errors.

H. Snort

Snort is a leading open-source network intrusion prevention system (IPS) capable of performing real-time traffic analysis and packet logging on IP networks. It excels in protocol analysis, content searching, and matching, and is used to detect a wide array of attacks, including buffer overflows, stealth port scans, CGI attacks, SMB probes, and OS fingerprinting attempts. Snort can operate as a packet sniffer like tcpdump, a packet logger for debugging network traffic, or a full-blown network intrusion prevention system that can block malicious packets inline. Users can deploy Snort using a comprehensive ruleset to define malicious activity and generate alerts. The support for IEC61850 is limited to MMS.

I. Wireshark

Wireshark is a powerful tool for analyzing IEC 61850 protocols, widely used in substation automation. It supports the dissection and analysis of GOOSE, MMS, and SV messages. This allows users to capture and decode real-time communication between IEDs, providing detailed insights into protocol behavior and facilitating troubleshooting. With built-in filters and display options, Wireshark enables users to isolate and examine specific types of IEC 61850 traffic, making it an essential tool for maintaining and optimizing substation networks.

IV. SIMULATION OF SUBSTATION OPERATION USING OPEN SOURCE TOOLS

The main objective is to simulate various configurations according to the IEC 61850 standard in a Romanian DSO 20kV/10kV substation. This configuration was chosen because it is commonly used in smart grid applications, which inherently present a higher cybersecurity risk. The integration of advanced digital communication and control systems in such substations makes them more susceptible to cyber threats, thereby providing an ideal environment for conducting comprehensive cybersecurity evaluations and enhancing the resilience of smart grid infrastructure. This substation, referred to as Substation X, will be modelled using Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7 equipment to facilitate

cybersecurity studies. Leveraging the SCL file provided by the OpenServer project, which outlines the architecture of a general substation with three IEDs, the simulation includes a Sampled Measured Values (SMV) publisher (merging unit) and a protection IED containing a Protection Trip Overcurrent (PTOC) function. This PTOC function triggers upon detecting an overcurrent, subsequently activating the Protection Trip Conditioning (PTRC) in the same Logical Device (LD). The PTOC receives sampled values from the merging unit, and the PTRC publishes a trip command via GOOSE messaging. Additionally, a Circuit Breaker (XCBR) IED subscribes to GOOSE messages from the PTRC and publishes its status value (stVal). Using OpenSCD, several adjustments were made to align the simulation with the operational conditions of a genuine Romanian substation, ensuring the model accurately reflects real-world scenarios - Fig. 2. The

Fig. 2: OpenSCD substation X SCL file modification

IEDs support simulated values from a SPICE model, allowing for the transmission of current and voltage measurements from the simulation to the IEDs. The interaction between the circuit breakers and disconnectors with the simulation creates a closed-loop system, integrating the SPICE model with the IED functions. This setup mimics real operation scenarios where attempting to open a disconnector under load results in an error due to interlocking constraints managed by the CILO logical node, which prevents the disconnector from operating if the circuit breaker is engaged. Also, when a current threshold is reached, the circuit breaker trips, which leads to the disconnector engaging. The disconnector can then be closed after the current value returns to normal - Fig. 3.

Once the successful operation of the substation is established in the simulated environment, the SCL file can be used to extract individual CID files for manual configuration of IEDs using IEDexplorer. Alternatively, the SCL file can be employed to restructure the entire power system design process, thereby eliminating the need for manual configuration. This approach minimizes manual data entry errors and reduces misunderstandings between system capabilities and requirements, ensuring a more efficient and accurate design and implementation process. Next, due to the limited online capabilities of OpenServer, CID files for the circuit breaker and disconnector were extracted and used for creating two equivalent IEDs used for online GOOSE communication.

V. ONLINE GOOSE COMMUNICATION AND CYBERSECURITY TESTING

Developing a testbed with simulated IEDs based on the obtained CID files for the circuit breaker and disconnector

(a) Simulated voltages.
(b) Simulated currents for the proposed scenario.
Fig. 3: OpenServer Substation X simulation.

involved the use of the LibIEC61850 library. These CID files were used to appropriately modify the **simpleIO-direct-control-goose.cid** file from the server GOOSE example. To emulate the IEDs, two Raspberry Pi 4 devices, each with 8 GB of RAM and running Ubuntu 24.04, were used. The LibIEC61850 library was compiled on both Raspberry Pi devices.

The testbed setup was completed with a Planet 8-port switch and a laptop running Wireshark to capture network traffic and conduct cybersecurity attacks against the GOOSE protocol. Once the GOOSE communication was successfully established, a clean packet was captured and analyzed - Fig. 4. From this packet, the relevant MAC addresses and packet details were extracted.

Fig. 4: GOOSE clean packet

A modified version of the packet was created, altering the state of a boolean value from false to true. This modified packet was then sent to the receiving IEDs using GESE 2.0 [19], to determine whether it would be accepted or dropped.

After several attempts, the modified packet was accepted, successfully demonstrating a false data injection attack (FDI) - Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Successful FDI attack.

This experiment highlighted potential vulnerabilities in the GOOSE protocol and underscored the importance of robust cybersecurity measures in protecting substation communication systems.

VI. DEVELOPING A LABORATORY TESTBED FOR CYBERSECURITY EVALUATION FOR DSO SUBSTATIONS

Communication plays a vital role in the real-time operation of power systems. Legacy protocols defined byte transmission but not data organization within devices, necessitating manual configuration by engineers. The IEC 61850 standard revolutionizes this by providing a comprehensive model for data organization, ensuring consistency across all devices and reducing manual configuration efforts. The primary advantage of our proposed approach lies in the use of physical IEDs with a TRL of 7, which provides a higher fidelity simulation compared to purely virtual models. Traditional approaches often rely on virtual IEDs or simulated environments [20] that lack the complexity and nuances of real-world applications. While useful, virtual simulations can oversimplify device interactions and fail to capture critical operational behaviours and vulnerabilities in actual substation environments. Traditional testing methods, such as those using legacy protocols or vendor-specific solutions, often require significant manual effort to configure devices and map power system variables to low-level register numbers or I/O modules. These methods are prone to errors and inconsistencies, leading to unreliable testing results. In contrast, the IEC 61850 standard automates this process through its comprehensive data organization model, reducing manual configuration efforts and ensuring more accurate and reliable simulations. Furthermore, the proposed approach leverages open-source tools like OpenServer, OpenSCD, and LibIEC61850, which offer flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and ease of modification. These tools create a realistic and adaptable testbed environment that can be easily updated and expanded as new cybersecurity threats emerge. This adaptability significantly improves over traditional proprietary solutions, which can be costly and less flexible.

Despite its strengths, the proposed approach has certain limitations. The current testbed is limited to specific configurations and components, which may not fully encompass the diversity of devices and setups in different substations. Additionally, the reliance on TRL 7 equipment, while ensuring

high fidelity, may not capture the behavior of older devices that are still in use in many substations.

Fig. 6: Laboratory testbed for cybersecurity DSO substation.

The end result, as shown in Fig. 6, consisted of the following components: an RTU SCU-CLP 500, a Modicon M580 PLC with an IEC 61850 communication module extension, a Siemens 7SJ82 bay protection unit, and a Cisco WS-C3650 Ethernet switch with Software-Defined Networking (SDN) capabilities. This configuration demonstrated the successful integration and interoperability of various devices from different manufacturers within the simulated Substation X.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This study developed and implemented a comprehensive laboratory testbed for cybersecurity evaluation of distribution substations, focusing on the GOOSE communication protocol as specified by IEC 61850. Utilizing open-source tools and TRL 7 level equipment, the testbed realistically mimics operational conditions of a real substation while ensuring safety and isolation from live systems. By creating a simulated substation environment with tools like OpenServer, OpenSCD, and LibIEC61850, the study thoroughly tested GOOSE communication protocols and identified potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities. The successful integration of components such as a Modicon M580 PLC, Siemens 7SJ82 bay protection unit, and Cisco WS-C3650 Ethernet switch validated the IEC 61850 standard's interoperability and robustness. The ability to perform false data injection attacks further highlighted the critical need for robust cybersecurity measures, underscoring the importance of high-fidelity simulations for developing effective strategies to protect critical infrastructure.

Future developments could include expanding the range of devices and configurations tested within the lab environment. Incorporating more diverse IEDs and network components would enhance the comprehensiveness of the cybersecurity evaluations. Additionally, integrating automated tools

for real-time threat detection and response would further strengthen the testbed's capability to assess and improve cybersecurity measures.

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